
Understanding Patient Safety and Reducing Medical Risks

Haifa Mansour Mohammed Alquthami

ABSTRACT

There are many patients have been affected negatively from several medical procedures. Although there are various steps to follow after and during any medical procedures. Yet, there are many threats on patient safety. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to understand the patient safety and to follow guidelines to ensure patient healthcare and to make recommendations to improve these guidelines. A questionnaire was created to understand the actual risk of different medical procedures. Depending on the results of the questionnaire, reducing medical complications and improving patients safety could be improved by enhancing safety awareness, staff training, and risk reporting systems.

KEYWORDS: medical complications, patient safety, medical risks.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
31 August 2023

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

1. INTRODUCTION

Patient safety is the foundation of good patient care, the unnerving fact that healthcare can harm us as well as heal us is the reason for suggesting that patient safety is the heart of healthcare quality (Vincent, C., 2011). Patient safety is now recognized in many countries, with global awareness fostered by the World Health Organization's World Alliance for patient safety. However, there are significant challenges to implement patient safety policies and practices (Emanuel, L., Berwick, D., Conway, J., Combes, J., Hatlie, M., Leape, L & Walton, M., 2009). As a result, Over more than two decades' medical errors have continued to be a major cause of death in the U.S. as well as in other countries. Despite the mandated implementation of error reporting systems in many states, less than 10 percent of errors are reported. Even when errors are reported, hospitals fail to take effective actions to prevent their reoccurrence. (Anderson, J. G., & Abrahamson, K., 2017). The occurrence of errors is caused by a combination of human factors and other system factors. However, medical errors have ranged from 30% to 80% (Garrouste-Orgeas, M., Philippart, F., Bruel, C., Max, A., Lau, N., & Misset, B. 2012). Furthermore, adverse events resulting from surgical interventions are actually more frequently related to errors occurring before or after the procedure than by technical surgical mistakes during the operation. (Kim, F. J., da Silva, R. D., Gustafson, D., Nogueira, L., Harlin, T., & Paul, D. L. 2015). However, medical staff must have wider knowledge about patient safety and how to reduce the medical risks of any procedure. As a result, this study

seeks to establish a better understanding for the importance of the patient's safety as well as reducing the Potential risks associated with any medical complications.

2. METHOD

This study used a questionnaire to assess if medical practitioners in Saudi Arabia (Riyadh) have enough knowledge with the patient safety. The purpose The questionnaire was designed to be brief due to the time constraints. As a result, the questionnaire contained eight multiple-choice questions (appendix 1 "the questionnaire template")

An online survey tool was used to create the questionnaire, and the survey link was then distributed to medical practitioners groups via Gmail (e.g. doctors and nurses). Data was gathered online (21 responses). The collected data was then classified based on the positions of the respondents in order to observe differences in perceptions among various groups of medical practitioners. Finally, data was analyzed in order to better understand and improve current safety of patients and to reduce the medical complications.

3. RESULTS

The sections of this paper that follow highlight the questionnaire results. The findings are divided into two categories: patient safety awareness, and reduction of medical complications (figure 1a-1b)

‘Awareness of patient safety is critical ’

‘Medical complications can be reduced by working as a coordinated team ’

(Figure 1a)

(Figure 1b)

4. DISCUSSION

Medical staff had slightly different understandings of patient safety and reducing medical complications. Furthermore, it was discovered that the staff do not link patients safety with reducing medical risks. This could be due to the limited awareness of the connection between the two. As a result, the medical staff might have developed a common understanding of how patients' safety is dependent on reducing medical risks. As a result, it is important for the medical to be aware of the importance of the risks that might threaten the patient's health. Moreover, it is crucial that "developing and improving the physical infrastructure of hospitals, providing necessary human resources, ensuring staff receive patient safety education and promoting 'good' communication and information systems were, in turn, all identified as processes and strategies critical to improving patient safety." (Pelzang, R., & Hutchinson, A. M., 2018). It is also essential for medical staff to take into consideration that effective patient healthcare can be accomplished by perfect team collaboration. Since Leadership in critical care teams is faced with major structural challenges. Teams usually consist of different professional groups (surgeons, anaesthesiologists, nurses), each with their discrete tasks but all responsible for the patient's safety (Künzle, B., Kolbe, M., & Grote, G., 2010). However, this study discovered that medical staff must develop better understanding of patient safety and how to reduce medical risks. Moreover, It was determined in other conducted studies that education provided to healthcare workers in the direction of medical error/error reporting, types and intensity of errors, and classification of errors according to patient outcomes is effective in improving the approach to error reporting. At present, technological methods present opportunities like distance training

systems, simulation education, etc. and the use and investigation of these, and similar methods, is suggested to be effective on patient safety and error reporting education. (Unal, A., & Seren, S., 2016).

5. LIMITATIONS

It should also be emphasized that there are limitations to this study. It should be noted that the level of awareness of how to maintain patient safety and to reduce risks varies globally. levels of awareness might differ among medical staff due to their knowledge. Furthermore, respondents might have better answers if they revealed their experience with their patients rather than using a questionnaires because they had to attempt a correct answers. However, this study provides an overview of medical complications and patients safety by shedding light general issues.

6. CONCLUSION

Ensuring patient safety is an important aspect for medical staff to consider. Some of the issues that are discussed in this study: levels of awareness among medical staff about patient's safety and how to reduce medical risks. However, there are important suggestions for improving the quality of patient's safety. Improvements can be achieved by extensive training of medical staff and appropriate use of patient care methods may be suggested. More research may be done to put the proposed improvements into practice in a hospital setting.

REFERENCES

- I. Anderson, J. G., & Abrahamson, K. (2017). Your health care may kill you: Medical errors. *ITCH*, 234, 13-17.

Understanding Patient Safety and Reducing Medical Risks

- II. Emanuel, L., Berwick, D., Conway, J., Combes, J., Hatlie, M.,
- III. Leape, L., ... & Walton, M. (2009). What exactly is patient safety?. *Journal of Medical Regulation*, 95(1), 13-24.
- IV. Kim, F. J., da Silva, R. D., Gustafson, D., Nogueira, L., Harlin,
- V. T., & Paul, D. L. (2015). Current issues in patient safety in surgery: a review. *Patient safety in surgery*, 9, 1-9.
- VI. Künzle, B., Kolbe, M., & Grote, G. (2010). Ensuring patient safety through effective leadership behaviour: a literature review. *Safety science*, 48(1), 1-17.
- VII. Leape, L. L. (1997). A systems analysis approach to medical error. *Journal of evaluation in clinical practice*, 3(3), 213-222.
- VIII. Pelzang, R., & Hutchinson, A. M. (2018). Patient safety issues and concerns in Bhutan's healthcare system: a qualitative exploratory descriptive study. *BMJ open*, 8(7), e022788.
- IX. Unal, A., & Seren, S. (2016). Medical error reporting attitudes of healthcare personnel, barriers and solutions: a literature review. *J Nurs Care*, 5(6), 377.
- X. Vincent, C. (2011). *Patient safety*. John Wiley & Sons.

Appendix 1

This questionnaire aims to understand and develop patient safety and reducing medical complications in hospital settings. Your answers will help to understand the current situation of patient safety in hospital environment. "This questionnaire is reused from *Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture Questionnaire* Uploaded by [Srinivas Polikepati](#)."

Position in the hospital:

To what extent to you agree with the following statements:

1) Nurse's opinion is well received in the clinic area

Strongly agree

Agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

2) in the clinic area, it is difficult to speak if I perceive a problem with the patient care

Strongly agree

Agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

3) Decision-making in the clinic area utilizes input from relevant practitioners

Strongly agree

Agree

Neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

4) The physicians and nurses in the clinic area work together as well coordinated team.

Strongly agree

Agree

Understanding Patient Safety and Reducing Medical Risks

Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

5) Disagreements in the clinic area are resolved appropriately. (i.e, not who is right, but what is the best for patient.)

Strongly agree

Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

6) It is easy for practitioners in the clinic area to ask questions when there's something that they don't understand.

Strongly agree

Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

7) I have the support I need from other practitioners to care for a patient.

Strongly agree

Agree
Neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

8) When thinking about risk, my primary focus is on the needs of:

Strongly agree

Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly disagree